

INTRAPERSONAL DETERMINANTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG DIFFERENTLY ABLED INDIVIDUALS

Nimra Munawar^{*1}, Seemab Shafiq², Syeda Shahida Batool³,
Muhammad Furkan Ullah Butt⁴

^{*1}Lecturer, Lahore School of Behavioural Science, the University of Lahore.

²Student Counsellor, Government College University Lahore.

³Professor of Psychology, Government College University, Lahore.

⁴Assistant Professor of Psychology, Govt. College Gulberg for Boys Lahore.

^{*1}nimra.munawar@lsbs.uol.edu.pk

Corresponding Author: *

Nimra Munawar

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16993295>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
29 May, 2025	04 July, 2025	04 August, 2025	29 August, 2025

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to investigate the relationship between demographic variables (i.e., gender, education, and types of disability) and intrapersonal variables (i.e., internal locus of control and grit) with psychological wellbeing among individuals with disabilities. This study aimed to test the basic assumption of Ryff's model of psychological well-being (Ryff, 1989). A sample of 156 individuals with disabilities (i.e., deaf, blind, and physically disabled), comprising 86 males and 70 females, with an age range of 15-35 years, was selected. A purposive sampling technique was used for data collection through Google Forms. Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale (Ryff & Keyes, 1995), the Grit-17 item scale (Angela Duckworth et al., 2007), and the Internal Locus of Control (Reid & Ware, 1974) were used. The results showed that psychological well-being was significantly and positively correlated with grit and internal locus of control. Grit and internal locus of control significantly predicted (17 percent variance) psychological wellbeing. The male participant showed a higher psychological well-being than the female participant. There was a significant mean difference in psychological wellbeing with respect to types of disability. Multivariate analysis revealed that education had no significant impact on psychological wellbeing, grit, or internal locus of control among individuals with disabilities. It was concluded that enhancing the grit and internal locus of control could improve the wellbeing of individuals with disabilities. This study has important implications for special education institutions.

Keywords: grit, psychological wellbeing, internal locus of control, differently abled individual.

INTRODUCTION

A physical impairment occurs when a person's body component or function is permanently lost or damaged, resulting in a decline in their level of strength, endurance, physical activity, and overall capacity. The person may be unable to perform everyday bodily functions, including walking, standing, sitting, using hands and arms, and controlling muscles, as a result of the functional loss. According to the World Health Organization (2001, 2011), "disability is a broader term that encompasses

physical, psychological, intellectual, and socio-emotional impairments and is defined in both legal and scientific ways." The US Democratic National Committee first used the word differently abled in the 1980s as an alternative word used to refer to disabilities and handicapped conditions. It was introduced with the intention of conveying a positive message and might help prevent discrimination against individuals with disabilities. In the Institute of Medicine's definition, handicap

was not specified as a disability factor. Disability is not an individual's intrinsic definition, but rather a contextual one – a feature of the person's relationship with social and physical environments. Their community determines a person's level of disability for any impairment (i.e., disability potential) as well as the existence (and severity) of a potentially incapacitating illness.

"Psychological wellbeing includes the ability to maintain a sense of autonomy, self-acceptance, personal growth, purpose in life, and self-esteem," according to the definition found in the International Encyclopedia of the Social and Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition), 2015 (Burgha, 2015). Psychological wellbeing refers to the intra-individual and inter-individual level of positive functioning, encompassing self-referential and connected feelings. It encompasses one's sense of mastery and personal development.

Subjective wellbeing (SWB) is the scientific word for contentment and happiness. Subjective wellbeing is one of the two key components. The first is that people experience happiness and pleasant emotions. Also referred to as "Hedonic" wellbeing, it is composed of two parts: an experiential affective part and a cognitive part. When positive effects and satisfaction are strong, people feel happy. The other is feeling the need to achieve something worthwhile and significant. It is referred to as "Eudaimonic." Carol Ryff created a model for psychological wellbeing in 1989. This paradigm states that a person's psychological wellbeing can be assessed using specific dimensions. Higher scores in these aspects indicate a greater or higher degree of psychological well-being, whereas lower scores indicate a lower level of well-being.

Ryff's Model of Psychological Well Being

A model for psychological wellbeing was proposed by Carol Ryff (1989). According to this model, there are certain dimensions by which a person's psychological wellbeing can be measured. Higher scores in these dimensions indicate a higher or increased level of psychological well-being, whereas lower scores represent a lower or decreased level of psychological well-being.

Self-acceptance is about having a positive attitude towards oneself. It refers to acknowledging and accepting different aspects of oneself, such as recognizing both good and bad, strengths and weaknesses, and talents. She accepts that he accepts her offer and feels positive about it. If a person scores

high in self-acceptance, then they are satisfied with life (achieve self-actualization). If his self-acceptance is low, he feels dissatisfied and disillusioned about his life.

Positive Relationship with Others. To develop a positive relationship with others, one should have warm, trusting, helpful, empathetic, and affectionate behavior towards others. A high score indicates that one cares about others and is supported by others. If a person scores lower, it means their relationship with others is weaker.

Autonomy. Autonomy means one is independent and self-determining. It is about when one person has confidence in their opinion, they can resist social pressures. Low scores indicate that the person is more concerned about others and tends to make decisions based on the judgments of others.

Environmental Mastery.

It is a perception of maturity when it comes to environmental management. A person is proficient in handling daily tasks and creates a suitable environment that meets their personal benefits and needs. High scores indicate that the person thinks they are in charge of the situation in which they live.

Purpose in Life.

One has a firm belief that there is a purpose to my life. High scores indicate that the person has a strong sense of direction and opinion, suggesting they have a clear life goal. People who score low tend to have few goals or a weak sense of purpose in life.

Personal Growth.

It means a person continues to develop, realizes their potential, and sees themselves growing and improving over time. Embracing positive change and self-acknowledgment, or trying new experiences in life. Low scores indicated that the person is afraid of new experiences and lacks self-improvement (Seifert, 2005).

Determinants of Psychological Wellbeing

Several factors contribute to psychological well-being, including both intrapersonal and interpersonal aspects. Intrapersonal determinants included perseverance, consistency, spirit, passion, attitudes, motivation, self-concept, and goal setting. Interpersonal determinants included social support, social relationships, and environmental factors.

Certain factors contribute to psychological well-being, including social, cultural, and personal factors. One group of factors, which is a personal factor, is controllable and can be worked on to enhance the acceptance of disability. This study focused on intrapersonal determinant (viz., grit, and internal locus of control).

Grit. "Grit is passion and sustained persistence applied toward long-term achievement, with no particular concern for rewards or recognition along the way," according to Angela Duckworth. To achieve goals that span months, years, or even decades, it requires a blend of self-control, ambition, and resilience (Duckworth, 2016). Grit: The strength of zeal and tenacity (Vol. 234).

Grit is an important personality trait. Its basic idea entails how a person pursues their goal with perseverance and passion. It plays an important role in glorifying one's consistency and hardworking capabilities, although natural tendencies may vary from person to person. Grit precedes talent, but it is still possible to be a successful person without talent. Grit in the human psyche was founded by Angela Duckworth (2016). Grit played a role not only in enhancing life satisfaction but also in decreasing depression (Jim & Kim, 2017). Researchers investigated measuring grit in young people both with and without disabilities. Results indicate that the grit persistence component significantly predicted grade point average for both groups, and the scale performs similarly for students with and without disabilities (Lombardi et al., 2019).

Locus of Control.

A vital aspect of personality in psychology is the Locus of control. Julian B. Rotter originally developed this concept in the 1950s, and since then, it has become an essential topic of study in personality psychology (Rotter, 1966). The word "Locus" is a Latin term meaning "place" or "location". The degree to which someone perceives themselves as being in control of their life and environment can be defined as the locus of control (Lefcourt, 1976). Essentially, you believe that you are either the controller of your life or controlled by external actors (such as luck, divine powers, or authoritative individuals). The assumption that the results of our actions depend on our actions (internal control orientation) or on circumstances beyond our control (external control orientation) is known as a locus of control orientation (Zimbardo, 1985, p. 275).

In 1999, Martz examined the relations between locus of control and disability acceptance. The goal of this research was to determine whether locus of control was associated with the acceptance of disability. The finding showed a strong relationship between individuals' modification scores and an external score of locus of control, as well as between the individuals' own modification scores and an internal score of locus of control. If an individual exhibits a greater internal locus of control, changes in accepting the disability would be higher (Martz, 2000). Papadopoulos (2014) investigated the impact of personal traits on the locus of control and self-esteem of young adults with visual impairments. The impact of personal factors (visual status, gender, age at onset of sight loss, duration of vision loss, education, mobility, and employment status) on locus of control (LOC) and self-esteem was investigated in this study. Age at the time of vision loss, vision status, the recentness of vision loss, and education have all been found to be significant determinants of self-esteem. Furthermore, mobility and eyesight status were important indicators of LOC (Papadopoulos, 2014).

External Locus of Control.

A high score indicates that individuals with a high external locus of control believe that outside forces are beyond their control; they often attribute their circumstances to external factors. They do not believe they can improve their situation through their own actions; they feel powerless and impoverished in difficult situations, even though they often attribute this to external factors (Cherry, 2019). "The extent to which people anticipate the outcome depends on chance, fate, or luck, is controlled by other strong entities, or simply cannot be predicted." Rotter (1990).

Internal Locus of Control.

A high internal locus of control indicates that people with ILC typically possess a strong sense of self-efficacy. People believe that they can control their own situation. They can take responsibility for their actions. An internal locus of control is desired, emphasizing self-determination and personal control. They work hard to achieve their goals, feel confident, are physically healthier, happier, and more independent. Others' opinions have less influence on them. They can achieve greater success; their own choices lead to success or failure (Cherry, 2019). People with an internal locus of control are

self-assured that the outcome of their activities depends on themselves (Andrisani, 1976), their capabilities (Carrim, 2006), or their stable personality and choices (Littunen, 2000). They are sure that efforts, personal talents, and personal effort produce productive results (Carrim, 2006). "The degree to which a person expects the result of their behavior is contingent on their own behavior or personal characteristics" (Rotter, 1990).

Stability.

Stability occurs when the locus of control factors is natural, encompassing both external and internal factors. There are four mutual attributes: ability (Internal), task difficulty (external), effort (Internal), and luck (external). Ability and task difficulty are equal to stability, while effort and luck are equal to unsuitability. An individual with a stable locus of control would attribute their failure to a lack of capability.

In contrast, a person with an unstable locus of control may blame it on being unfortunate or unlucky (Cherry, 2019). Nierenberg et al. (2016) investigated the use of wellbeing treatment for people with chronic illnesses and disabilities. The majority of individuals with impairment are reverting to their pre-morbid psychological states, according to clinical research. Nonetheless, many people with disabilities are susceptible to mental health issues like anxiety, depression, and posttraumatic stress disorder. The paper then examines the effects of offering practical treatments that can enhance the quality of life for people with disabilities and chronic illnesses.

According to this perspective, wellness therapy is recommended as an intervention, as it has demonstrated efficacy in preventing the emergence of specific harmful states. The concepts and elements of this strategy apply to both individuals with disabilities and the fundamentals of recovery psychology. By combining key wellbeing components, this examines a strategy for motivating individuals with disabilities to enhance their wellbeing and reduce detrimental aspects of their lives. The researchers conclude by talking about the advantages of general wellbeing and the traditional emphasis on reducing solely negative emotional states (Nierenberg et al., 2016).

Dardick et al. (2017) investigated the relationship between learning disabilities and non-cognitive skills—namely, mindset, grit, and optimism—in adolescents. Using items from the Implicit Theories

of Intelligence Scale (Dweck, 2000), Self-Theory (De Castella & Byrne, 2015), Short Grit Scale (Duckworth & Quinn, 2009), and Life Orientation Test–Revised (Scheier et al., 1994), they found significant correlations among these variables and preliminary evidence of scale reliability for this group. Despite the small sample size, the study provides an initial analysis of these constructs in adolescents with learning disabilities. Lombardi et al. (2019) examined grit in adolescents with and without disabilities ($n = 5,039$) to test its measurement consistency across both groups. Results showed the grit scale functioned similarly, with the perseverance factor linked to higher average grades in both groups. The study supports the use of this scale in school-level data collection and transition planning within career and college readiness programs.

Rationale

Some research has provided a rationale for the present research. In the past, research has been conducted to study the internal locus of control and the relationship between disabilities and their family members with disabilities in individuals with different abilities. There is research on intrapersonal determinants of psychological well-being in the West and the Middle East, not in Pakistan. The research is conducted on various populations, with a specific focus on individuals with disabilities. This study examines the relationship between intrapersonal determinants (grit, internal locus of control) and psychological well-being among individuals with disabilities. This research would be a great contribution to the literature.

The primary objective of this study is to examine the relationships between demographic variables (gender, education, and disability), intrapersonal factors (grit and internal locus of control), and psychological wellbeing among individuals with disabilities. Specifically, it aims to assess the predictive strength of demographic factors, grit, and internal locus of control in determining psychological well-being, as well as to explore group differences in psychological well-being based on gender, type of disability, and educational level. It is hypothesized that grit, internal locus of control, and psychological wellbeing will exhibit significant positive relationships. Furthermore, significant associations are expected between demographic variables (gender, age, education level, and number of siblings) and the psychological constructs under

study. It is also anticipated that demographic factors, grit, and internal locus of control will significantly predict psychological wellbeing. Additional hypotheses propose that gender differences will exist in grit, internal locus of control, and psychological well-being; that educational level will contribute to differences in these variables; and that types of disability will result in significant variations in psychological well-being.

Method

Research design

Quantitative Correlation research design was used. The sample of this study comprised 156 participants (86 males and 70 females) with an age range of 15 to 35 years. The target population consisted of individuals with disabilities from various

institutions and welfare organizations. In this study, individuals with disabilities, including those who are deaf, blind, or physically disabled, who met the criteria, were approached and included in the study. A purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data, as it met the theoretical needs of the study. Individuals who did not meet the criteria were excluded from the sample before conducting the analysis. The current pandemic situation necessitated reducing the research sample from 400 to 156. All responses were collected using a questionnaire developed on Google Forms. Links to this questionnaire were shared with various special persons' institutes, welfare organizations, and via WhatsApp groups, as well as through personal messages, using convenience sampling.

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics of the Participants (N= 156)

Variables	f (%)	M(SD)
Gender		24.4(5.4)
Male	86(54.8)	
Female	70(44.6)	
Education Level		3(1.6)
Matric	28(17.8)	
Intermediate	40(25.5)	
B.A	30(19.1)	
M.A	22(14.0)	
BS(hons)	20(12.7)	
Mphil	6(3.8)	
Age		24.4(5.4)
Adolescence	85(54.1)	
Young adult	70(44.6)	
Family System		1.6(.57)
Joint	63(40.1)	
Nuclear	91(58.0)	
Father's profession		5(1.7)
Doctor	3(1.9)	
Engineer	7(4.5)	
Business man	25(15.9)	
Army/ police	3(1.9)	
Worker	62(39.5)	
Government job	23(14.6)	
Teacher	14(8.9)	
Other	18(11.5)	
Disability		2.1(.84)
Blind	66(42.0)	

Deaf	43(27.4)
Physically disable	43(27.4)

Note: f: frequency, %: percentage

Inclusion criteria

This sample included individuals with physical disabilities, deafness, and blindness.

Exclusion criteria

Individuals with intellectual and learning disabilities and without any disabilities were excluded from this study, and those who were below age 15 and above age 35 were also excluded.

Instruments

The following scales were used in this study.

Demographic Information Sheet

The Demographic Information Sheet included age, gender, education level, number of siblings, family structure, father's occupation, and type of disability.

Ryff's Psychological Wellbeing Scale (Ryff & Keyes, 1995)

Psychological well-being, as measured by Ryff's (1989) scale of PWB, comprises six dimensions: self-acceptance, positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and personal growth. It is the most widely adopted scale to measure psychological wellbeing. This research uses the 42-item version to measure the six proposed dimensions of PWB. Items like "Most people see me as loving and affectionate" and "Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me." Each item is rated on a 6-point scale (1) strongly disagree to (6) strongly agree. There are positively and negatively worded items, and the mean score was obtained after item reversal of selected items. The scale exhibits good internal reliability, with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value of 0.82. This study also reveals that the Cronbach's alpha coefficient value was 0.78.

Grit Scale by Angela Duckworth et al. (2007)

Grit was measured using Angela Duckworth's Duckworth's Duckworth's 17-item scale (Duckworth, 2017). This scale evaluates a person's level of grit, which is comparable to their passion and struggle in achieving long-term goals.

Respondent answers each item on a 5-point scale extending from 1 (not like me at all) to 5 (very much like me). The scale has good internal reliability, with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value of .85. The value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient in this study was .67. A comprehensive pilot study was undertaken to check the reliability of the scale. The results obtained from the 17th item scale are more convincing than those from the 8th and 12th item scales.

Internal Locus of Control by Reid And Ware (1974)

The internal locus of control was measured using Reid and Ware's 8-item short version. The 45-item scale breaks down the concept of locus of control into three sub-dimensions. The current study utilized one of the sub-dimensions of self-control: the capability to regulate one's own feelings and impulses. Respondent answers each item on a 6-point scale extending from 1 (completely agree) to 6 (completely disagree). The scale exhibits good internal reliability, as evidenced by a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value of 0.83.

Ethical Considerations

Before participating, all participants were briefed on the purpose and key aspects of the study via an introductory note to the survey. They were informed that their participation is voluntary and they can opt out at any time, before, during, or after completing the survey questionnaire. Participants were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and that the research would be conducted responsibly.

Procedure

First, permissions to use the scales were obtained from their authors (see Annexure -A). The data were collected from individuals with disabilities from different institutions and welfare organizations. Different institutes and organization were considered to keep the study versatile and not bound to any specific institutes. The scales were translated into Urdu, taking into account the participants' level of understanding. This Urdu-translated scale was then back-translated by two

English professors to verify the validity of the translated scale. Participants were advised to provide honest responses, and consent forms were also obtained. All respondents guaranteed that they would keep their details private/ confidential.

Result

The data collected for the present study were analyzed using SPSS. To achieve the study's goals and evaluate the hypotheses, data were analyzed using appropriate statistical measures to determine the impact of psychological wellbeing, gender differences, types of disability, education level, and the relationships among the variables. Pearson's product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship among the variables. Stepwise regression was used to determine whether psychological wellbeing predicts internal locus of

control and grit. An independent sample *t*-test analysis was used to assess the mean difference in variables between male and female participants. ANOVA analysis was used to determine the significant difference in means between the levels of disability. MANOVA analysis was employed to examine the effect of education level on psychological wellbeing, grit, and internal locus of control.

The results in Table 2 show that Cronbach's Alpha of Psychological Wellbeing Scale is .78. Results also show that Cronbach's Alpha of Internal Locus of Control Reid-Ware Scale is .83. These results show that both scales are highly reliable. Moreover, the results also show that Cronbach's Alpha for the Grit-17 items is .67, which is also reliable.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics and Reliability Coefficients for Grit, Internal Locus of Control, and Psychological Wellbeing (N=156)

Scales	α	k	M	SD	Range		Skewness
					Potential	Actual	
Psychological wellbeing	.78	42	160.67	20.65	42-252	126-227	.95
Internal locus of control	.83	8	33.55	7.67	8-48	8-48	-.91
Grit	.67	17	3.30	.53	17-85	2-4	.40

Note. α = reliability coefficient, k no. of items in scale

Results in Table 3 indicate that Cronbach's Alpha for the Subscale Autonomy is .36, which suggests that this subscale is not reliable. Cronbach's Alpha value for the Environmental Mastery sub-scales is -.11, which indicates a problem. Cronbach's Alpha

values for the positive relation and purpose in life sub-scales are .37 and .30, respectively. This indicates that neither of these sub-scales has good reliability. So, we cannot use these subscales in this study.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics and Reliability Coefficients for Study Psychological Wellbeing Sub-Scales (N=156)

Scales subscales	α	k	M	SD	Range		Skewness
					Potential	Actual	
Autonomy	.36	7	26.25	4.96	7-42	8-42	.39
Environmental Mastery	-.11	7	24.63	3.86	7-42	12-37	.16

Personal growth	.50	7	27.93	5.55	7-42	13-42	.31
Positive relation	.37	7	27.45	4.93	7-42	15-40	.37
Purpose in life	.30	7	26.25	4.84	7-42	12-41	.31
Self-acceptance	.51	7	27.52	5.31	7-42	16-42	.36

Note. α = reliability coefficient; k no. Of items in the subscale

Table 4 shows a highly significant positive correlation between psychological well-being and grit ($r = 0.38, p < 0.001$). The result also shows a positive and significant correlation between psychological well-being and an internal locus of control. ($r=.28, p < .01$). It also shows that there is a positive and significant week correlation between

gender and psychological well-being ($r=.17, p < .01$). The results show that there is a positive and highly significant correlation between grit and internal locus of control ($r=.29, p < .001$). Results have shown that there is a positive, significant, and weak correlation between gender and grit ($r = .08, p < .05$). Additionally, it indicates a positive and highly significant correlation between grit and age ($r = .20, p < .001$).

Table 4 Pearson Product-Moment Correlation between Psychological Wellbeing, Grit, Internal Locus of Control, Gender, Age, and Disability

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	M(SD)
1. PWB	-	.38***	.28***	.17**	-.05	160(20)
2. Grit	-	-	.29***	.08*	.20**	3.3(.53)
3. ILC	-	-	-	-.02	.09*	33(7.67)
4. Gender	-	-	-	-	-.07*	1.55(.49)
5. Age	-	-	-	-	-	24(5.47)

Note: * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$; PWB= Psychological Well-being; ILC=Internal Locus of Control

In Table 5, stepwise linear regression is employed to investigate the predictors of grit and internal locus of control on psychological well-being. In model 1, Grit is found to be a significant predictor of psychological wellbeing. The value of R^2 indicated that grit can explain 14% of the variance in psychological well-being ($F(147) = 24.79, p = .001, \beta = .38, t = 4.98$). In model 2, internal locus of control

is found to be a significant predictor of psychological wellbeing. The value of R^2 indicated that the interaction effect of both grit and internal locus of control can explain 17% of the variance in psychological well-being. So, internal locus of control has 3% variance in psychological wellbeing. ($F(146) = 5.26, p < .01, \beta = .18, p = .001$).

Table 5 Regression Analysis to Calculate Predictability of Grit and Internal Locus of Control on Psychological Wellbeing (N= 156)

Variables	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	SE	β	B	SE	β
Grit	14.60	2.93	.38	12.41	3.04	.32
Internal locus of control				.48	.21	.18

R ²	.14	.17
F	24.79***	5.26**

Note. β =Coefficient of Regression, *** $p < .00$, ** $p < .01$
In Table 6, the Independent Sample t-test indicates a significant difference in psychological well-being between male students ($M = 163.97$, $SD = 22.45$) and

female students ($M = 156.60$, $SD = 17.54$). The value of Cohen's d indicated a small effect size between the male and female groups in psychological well-being.

Table 6 Independent Sample t-test (N=156)

Variables	Male (n=86)		Female (n=70)		t	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Grit	3.34	.537	3.25	.537	-1.05	.29	-.26	.07	0.16
ILC	33.34	8.59	33.80	6.41	.37	.70	-1.92	2.82	0.06
PWB	163.97	22.45	156.6	17.54	-2.24	.02	-13.82	-.87	0.36

Note. CI= confidence interval; LL: lower limit; UL= upper limit M = mean; SD = standard deviation; ILC= Internal Locus of Control; PWB= Psychological Well-being

In Table 7, the results indicate a significant mean difference among levels of disability in terms of psychological well-being. So we can use post hoc analysis for an in-depth study.

Table 7 One-Way Independent Sample ANOVA for Three Groups of Disability (N=156)

Variables	SS	df	MS	F	p
Disability	1237.24	2	2474.48	2.97*	.05

Note: * $p < .05$

In Table 7.1, the results indicate significant mean differences in psychological well-being among differently abled participants ($F 2.97$, $p=.05$). Post hoc analysis further indicates that there is a significant mean difference between physically

disabled and deaf ($p < .05$) and deaf and blind ($p < .05$) in terms of psychological well-being.

Table 7.1 Post hoc Analysis for Comparing Mean Differences between Three Groups of disability and Psychological Wellbeing

Psychological wellbeing				
Variable	Groups		Mean Difference	p
Disability	Blind	Physically disabled	.04	.99

	Deaf	9.07*	.02
Deaf	Physically disabled	-9.03*	.04
	Blind	-9.07*	.02
Physically disabled	Deaf	9.03*	.04
	Blind	-.04	.99

Note: * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

Discussion

This study aimed to assess the role of intrapersonal determinants (viz., grit and internal locus of control) in psychological Wellbeing among differently abled individuals. Pearson correlation analysis was run to test the first hypothesis. The results showed that psychological well-being has a significant positive and moderate correlation with the intrapersonal variables of grit and internal locus of control (See Table 4). Existing literature also supports our findings that individuals with a strong sense of direction and a clear life aim tend to have high psychological well-being (Maurer & Daukantaite, 2015; Fessler, 2020). A study conducted by Nierenberg et al. (2016) also supports the current finding that wellbeing therapy among differently abled participants is recommended as an intervention, as it has proven its efficacy in serving as a barrier against the creation of such negative affective states (Nierenberg et al., 2016). Another study by Crehan (2015) also supports the current finding that when a person with a disability has a high score on grit, they are more likely to minimize obstacles to achieving their life goals (Crehan, 2015). Individuals with disabilities have an internal locus of control, which enables them to overcome environmental challenges in their daily lives and maintain strong psychological well-being. The study by Martz et al. (2000) is also consistent with the current study's results, which indicate that persons with an internal locus of control have a higher acceptance of disability (Martz et al., 2000). Results show a positive and highly significant correlation between grit and internal locus of control (See Table 4). The results are not in line with those of Roshini and Zinna (2019), who found no correlation between locus of control and grit among athletes and non-athletes. The cause of this difference is that previous research has emphasized the internal-external locus of control, specifically in relation to athletes and non-athletes. The current study focuses

on the internal locus of control, particularly among individuals with disabilities.

Pearson's correlation analysis also indicated that demographic variables partially correlate with study variables (See Table 4). As a significant relationship between gender and psychological well-being and grit concerns, the results are consistent with previous studies. Research by Matud et al. (2019) showed that men reported higher psychological well-being than women. This finding is consistent with a previous study, which showed significant differences between females and males in the passion factor (grit) and attributed higher grit to male participants (Sigmundsson et al., 2020). Due to the stereotypical expectations of society, the well-being and grit levels of men are usually higher than those of women. Age also showed significant correlations only with grit and internal locus of control in the present study (see Table 4). The results are partially consistent with the previous literature. The results are consistent with this previous finding that there was a significant interaction between locus of control and age (Hickson et al., 1988). As people age, their grit level also increases. Because, in every way, age complements the grit level, and it is undeniably directly related to it.

The results of the regression analysis showed that intrapersonal determinants (internal locus of control and grit) were significant predictors of psychological wellbeing (see Table 5). This finding is consistent with research conducted by Vainio and Daukantaite (2016), which suggests that grit is a significant predictor of well-being (Vainio & Daukantaite, 2016; Jin & Kim, 2017). People who engage in activities that benefit from higher levels of sustained interest and perseverance by investing in the idea of self-growth and pursuing their personal goal, thereby reaching their well-being, which can be predicted by grit. The Griff and Gore's (2014) study did not support the results of the current study, showing that internal locus of

control had no unique variance in psychological wellbeing (Griff & Gore, 2014). It may be due to the reason that the sample differs from Griff and Gore's research. Differently abled individuals who internally control their lives through effort and a positive attitude become proactive, and this ultimately impacts their well-being. The result of this study is consistent with Stocks' (2012) cross-cultural study, which found a significant correlation between subjective well-being and locus of control, indicating that higher subjective well-being is well attributed to a higher internal locus of control. Klonowicz (2001) found that reactivity and locus of control were significant determinants of subjective well-being. Higher internal control is related to a more positive effect.

An independent sample *t*-test was conducted to examine group differences in psychological Well-Being. The results showed that male participants had higher psychological well-being than female participants (See Table 6). Research by Larson (2008) consistently shows that female spouses reported a lower quality of life and well-being than their male counterparts (Aslam & Zeeshan, 2007; Larson et al., 2008). In a society where the dominance of men is considered a divine right, there is a despotic tendency for men to be held as assertive rather than women. There is a greater chance for them to be psychologically healthy due to their massive exposure and favorable optimum conditions. Due to limited exposure and unfavorable circumstances, women often fall short of physical and psychological maturity.

The results of the MANOVA showed that there were no significant mean differences in intrapersonal determinants (grit and internal locus of control) and psychological wellbeing with respect to educational level (See Table 8). These findings of the study are inconsistent with those of Shikyoo and Kwon (2013), who stated that educated individuals with disabilities were more likely to cope better with their disability than those without education (Shikyoo & Kwon, 2013; Bengtsson & Gupta, 2017). The reason might be that there are cultural differences between previous research and current research. There are differences between the educational systems of individuals with typical development and those with disabilities. Normal students can achieve their goals smoothly in the educational sector, but differently abled individuals face difficulties in doing so. There is no friendly

environment in the educational or public sectors for them.

The ANOVA results also showed significant mean differences between the deaf and blind, and the deaf and physically disabled, in terms of psychological well-being (see Tables 6 and 7). The results are consistent with a previous study, which stated that the wellbeing of blind individuals was higher than that of individuals with other disabilities (Mirandola et al., 2019). This higher well-being can be attributed to their lack of awareness of others' facial expressions. The facial expression of others gives an individual the impression of being evaluated. The well-being of the deaf is good, as they cannot hear the different tones of voices. Physically disabled individuals scored lower on wellbeing compared to those who are blind or deaf. We can attribute this lower score to their inability to move independently and participate in activities that require physical mobility.

Implications

The findings of this study are applicable to educational and family settings involving individuals with special needs. It is helpful to understand the role of personal qualities in the well-being of individuals with disabilities, and this understanding can be beneficial for organizations, institutions, and schools that support persons with special needs, as well as family counselors. This study aims to encourage individuals with disabilities and improve their intrapersonal qualities. This study revealed that Grit is an important variable for individuals with disabilities. To develop Grit among differently abled individuals (special persons), organizations are recommended to conduct training.

Limitations and Suggestions

The sample size of the current study was relatively small due to the pandemic situation. A larger and more diverse sample should be used to ensure that the results can be generalized. This study was conducted through an online survey, so participants may not have been able to fill out the questionnaires with the same level of attention. The current study was based on young adults and adolescents. However, further research can be conducted on middle-aged or older persons. The study used a quantitative research design; in the future, a qualitative research method is recommended. A longitudinal research design can also be adopted to examine the long-term impact of grit and internal

locus of control on the well-being of individuals with disabilities. The socio-economic status of the participant was not well reported in the current study. Further research suggests that including the socio-economic status of participants in the study would be beneficial. The current study assessed only intrapersonal variables. Further study should include more variables, such as the External locus of control, meaning in life, as well as interpersonal variables.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the current study, we conclude that the well-being of individuals with disabilities varies due to differences in their personal qualities. So there is a dire need to formulate a policy on designing programs to enhance the intrapersonal qualities of individuals with disabilities, as male participants show better well-being than female participants. So we may conclude that women/girls with different disabilities are more vulnerable to suffering from psychological problems.

Références

- Bengtsson, S., & Datta Gupta, N. (2017). Identifying the effects of education on the ability to cope with a disability among individuals with disabilities. *PLoS One*, 12(3), e0173659. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0173659>
- Book Summary - Grit: The Power of Passion and Perseverance. (2019, March 19). Retrieved August 24, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4037/ccn2020905>
- Burns R. (2016). Psychosocial Wellbeing. In: Pachana N. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Geropsychology*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-080-3_251-1
- Carrim, N.M.H., Basson, J., & Coetzee, M. (2006). The Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Locus of Control in a South African Call Center Environment. *South African Journal of Labour Relations*, 30(2), 66-81. <https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/sabinet/1ht5j5/2006/00000030/0000002/art00005>
- Cherry, K. (2019, December 07). Are You in Control of Your Destiny, or Are You at the Mercy of Chance? <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-locus-of-control-2795434>
- Duckworth, A., & Duckworth, A. (2016). *Grit: The power of passion and perseverance* (Vol. 234). New York, NY: Scribner. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12198>
- Fessler, L. (2020, April 30). "You are no genius." Her father's shutdowns made Angela Duckworth a world expert on perseverance, also known as grit. <https://qz.com/work/1233940/angela-duckworth-explains-grit-is-the-key-to-success-and-self-confidence/>
- Hickson, J., Housley, W. F., & Boyle, C. (1988). The relationship of locus of control, age, and sex to life satisfaction and death anxiety in older persons. *The International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, 26(3), 191-199. <https://doi.org/10.2190/E5CK-THBM-QVOG-C3DN>
- Jin, B., & Kim, J. (2017). Grit, basic needs satisfaction, and subjective wellbeing. *Journal of Individual Differences*, 38(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1614-0001/a000219>
- Kim, S. J., & Kang, K. A. (2003). Meaning of life for adolescents with a physical disability in Korea. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 43(2), 145-155. https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2003.02689_1.x
- Larson, J., Franzén-Dahlin, Å., Billing, E., von Arbin, M., Murray, V., & Wredling, R. (2008). The impact of gender regarding psychological wellbeing and general life situation among spouses of stroke patients during the first year after the patients' stroke event: A longitudinal study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 45(2), 257-265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2006.08.021>
- Lefcourt, H. M. (1976). Locus of control and the response to aversive events. *Canadian Psychological Review/Psychologie Canadienne*, 17(3), 202. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0081839>

- Littunen, H., & Storhammar, E. (2000). The indicators of locus of control in the small business context. *Journal of Enterprise Culture*, 8, 343-360.
<https://doi.org/10.1142/S021849580000188>
- Lombardi, A. R., Rifenshield, G. G., Freeman, J., & Harvey, M. W. (2019). Measuring grit in adolescents with and without disabilities. *Journal of Disability Policy Studies*, 30(2), 67-77. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1044207319863635>
- Martz, E. (2003). Invisibility of disability and work experience as predictors of employment among community college students with disabilities. *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation*, 18(3), 153-161.
<https://content.iospress.com/articles/journal-of-vocational-rehabilitation/jvr00192>
- Nierenberg, B., Mayersohn, G., Serpa, S., Holovatyk, A., Smith, E., & Cooper, S. (2016). Application of wellbeing therapy to people with disability and chronic illnesses. *Rehabilitation psychology*, 61(1), 32. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rep0000060>
- Papadopoulos, K. (2014). The Impact of Individual Characteristics on Self-Esteem and Locus of Control in Young Adults with Visual Impairments. *Research in developmental disabilities*, 35(3), 671-675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2013.12.009>
- Rotter, J. B. (1966). Generalized expectancies for internal versus external control of reinforcement. *Psychological Monographs: General & Applied*, 80 (1), 1-28.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/h0092976>
- Ryff, C. (2014). Psychological wellbeing revisited: Advances in the science and practice of eudaimonia.
<https://doi.org/10.1159/000353263>
- Seifert, T. (2005). Assessment of the Ryff scales of psychological well-being. Retrieved October 23, 2010.
https://www.wabash.edu/alumni/news.cfm?news_ID=3570
- Sigmundsson, H., Haga, M., & Hermundsdottir, F. (2020). Passion, grit and mindset in young adults: Exploring the relationship and gender differences. *New Ideas in Psychology*, 59, 100795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.newideapsych.2020.100795>
- Tuckwiller, B. D., Dardick, W. R., & Kutscher, E. L. (2017). Profiles of and correlations among mindset, grit, and optimism in adolescents with learning disabilities: A pilot study. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies in Education*, 6(1), 43-62.
<https://isejournal.org/index.php/jise/article/view/186>
- Vainio, M. M., & Daukantaitė, D. (2016). Grit and different aspects of wellbeing: Direct and indirect relationships via sense of coherence and authenticity. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 17(5), 2119-2147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-015-9688-7>
- Yoo, Y. S., & Kwon, S. S. (2013). Effects of Education for Persons with Disabilities on Non-disabled Children's Attitudes toward Disabled Children. *The Journal of the Korea Contents Association*, 13(4), 508-517.
<https://doi.org/10.5392/JKCA.2013.13.04.508>
- Zeeshan, M., & Aslam, N. (2013). Resilience and psychological wellbeing among congenitally blind, late blind and sighted individuals. *Journal of Educational Research and Studies*, 1(1), 1-7. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235779674_Resilience_and_psychological_well-being_among_congenitallyblind_late_blind_and_sighted_individuals